

Mitigating Query Rot: Using Snapquery for Sustainable SPARQL Query Set Management

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Abstract. As RDF and knowledge graph solutions scale, the ability to execute federated queries across multiple endpoints becomes critical. However, current solutions’ stability depends on technical details that lack proper abstraction. For instance, SPARQL requires SERVICE statements with hard-coded endpoint URLs, potentially leading to what we term “query rot”. Even seemingly straightforward queries, such as the Wikidata “Cats” query, are susceptible to this structural vulnerability, highlighting the need for more robust query design mechanisms.

To address these limitations, we introduce the *snapquery* SPARQL middleware for query execution monitoring and analysis and refactoring. By applying the information hiding and dependency inversion principles, our approach hides query details to maintain behavior independently of technical implementation and context. This enables endpoint swapping and conceals federated query complexity. The increased abstraction aligns with state-of-the-art artificial intelligence approaches for natural language query generation.

This novel, systematic, and semi-automatic approach is generally useful in most knowledge graph management scenarios. By enabling on-the-fly collection of query metadata from real-world environments, we support the creation of test suites, benchmarks, challenges, dashboards, and other analytical applications for query performance and health monitoring. Our approach contributes to advancing knowledge engineering by bridging gaps between knowledge graphs, software engineering, and large language models.

We reproduce use cases of the Scholia, QLever and general Wikidata projects to demonstrate functionality and measure relevant quality metrics over those projects.

Keywords: SPARQL · Query Rot · Knowledge Graph Management · Quality Assessment · Refactoring · snapquery · Benchmarking · Sustainability

1 Introduction

Listing 1.1: SPARQL Query for Cats

```

SELECT ?item ?itemLabel
  WHERE {
    # Must be a cat
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q146.
    SERVICE wikibase:label {
      bd:serviceParam
        wikibase:language "[
          AUTO_LANGUAGE],en".
    }
  }

```

Fig. 1: Cats query result (`snapquery -queryName Cats -limit 6`)

item	itemLabel
Q378619	CC
Q498787	Muezza
Q677525	Orangey
Q851190	Mrs. Chippy
Q893453	Unsinkable Sam
Q1050083	Catmando
...	...

The *Cats* query⁴, a widely-used example in Wikidata’s SPARQL documentation, illustrates a critical challenge in knowledge graph infrastructure: *query rot*. This phenomenon, analogous to link rot in web content, refers to the gradual deterioration of query validity over time due to changes in the underlying *Query Execution Context (QEC)* (see Section 4). Even simple queries may fail as infrastructure evolves, particularly when queries depend on specific endpoint implementations or contain hard-coded URLs.

To address this challenge, we introduce *snapquery*: a tool and method that facilitates systematic query refactoring through automation. Queries are treated as first-class citizens, each with a fully qualified name and persistent identifier, following established principles for FAIR data management [34]. The approach applies software engineering principles of information hiding and dependency inversion (see Section 3.1), dividing queries into a *black-box* abstract part (query signature and parameters) and a *white-box* part (execution context details).

This separation serves different audiences effectively: the black-box view for end users and system integrators, and the white-box view for scholars and developers. Our research addresses three core research questions: (1) How can query rot be systematically mitigated? (2) How do software engineering principles improve query maintainability? (3) What is the impact of Named Parameterized Queries on real-world systems prone to query rot?

snapquery enables faster, systematic query refactoring by capturing metadata about functional and non-functional aspects of each named query. The tool automatically gathers and analyzes execution metadata with Large-Language-Model support, facilitating proactive maintenance and testing. This paper demonstrates *snapquery*’s effectiveness through three use cases:

- **Wikidata** – SPARQL examples and tutorials
- **Scholia** – Scholarly publishing
- **QLever** – SPARQL engine development

⁴ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/queries/examples#Cats

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 defines query rot and presents our use cases. Section 3 covers prior work. Section 4 details snapquery’s approach, Section 5 its implementation, and Section 6 its evaluation. Section 7 concludes with future directions.

2 Query Rot

2.1 Motivating use cases

Table 1: Motivating Use Cases and Query Sets

Use Case	Namespace	Name Example	# Queries
Wikidata	examples@wikidata.org	Cats	302
	short-url@wikidata.org	Japanese_Libraries_Details	100
	federated-queries	Editors of the WOP 2014	11
	@bitplan.com		
Subtotal			413
Scholia	named-queries	author_list-of-publications	373
	@scholia.toolforge.org		
	challenge@ceur-ws.org	AllVolumes	28
	WikidataThesisToolkit	LSE-doctoral-theses	27
@wikidata.org			
Subtotal			428
QLever	issues-wikidata	Issue858-query1	181
	@qllever.cs.uni-freiburg.de		
	performance-dblp	All papers published in SIGIR	6
	@qllever.cs.uni-freiburg.de		
examples@dblp.org	PublicationTypes	5	
Subtotal			192
Total			1033

Table 1 shows the relevant use cases and query sets that have motivated the snapquery approach and tool and that are presented in this work. Similar initiatives include the SPARQL examples repository by SIB [4], which documents over a 1000 bioinformatics question/query pairs over federated graphs.⁵

Wikidata SPARQL examples and usage The Wikidata SPARQL Service examples wiki page⁶ has accumulated over 300 queries since 2016, illustrating

⁵ This queryset will be imported in snapquery format soon

⁶ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/queries/

Wikidata’s usage. These queries are expected to work against the Wikidata service endpoint. However, this work reveals that this is not always the case and introduces methods to systematically analyze the reasons.

Wikidata’s query service (WDQS)⁷ offers a service to create short URLs for entered queries such a short URL may be considered as a pseudo-PID for the query. Such URLs do not provide any further metadata, though. A random set of 100 such queries has been included for investigation in this study to show how LLM generated addition of such metadata is feasible useful. A set of manually curated federated queries completes the Wikidata use case query sets, totaling 413 queries.

Scholia and Scholarly Publishing *Scholia*⁸ is a project allowing users to search, browse, and analyze scholarly publishing data curated in the Wikidata knowledge graph [24]. It uses named parameterized SPARQL queries which are implemented manually with Python, Jinja Templates and JavaScript.

Scholia faces challenges due to Wikidata’s size limitations. The Blazegraph SPARQL engine backing Wikidata can hold up to 4 Terabytes, which is insufficient for the vast amount of scholarly publishing data available [10]. The Wikimedia Foundation’s decision to split the graph and migrate scholarly data to its own knowledge graph potentially invalidates all 373 current Scholia queries.

The query sets of 428 queries for the Scholia use case come from multiple sources: 373 named queries extracted from Scholia’s GitHub repository, 28 Semantic Publishing Challenge [18] queries presented in our research Semantic MediaWiki⁹, and WikidataThesisToolkit [35] queries documented on a wiki page.

QLever SPARQL Engine Development

QLever is a high-performance SPARQL engine written in C++ [3]. It is a potential replacement for Blazegraph as Wikidata’s main SPARQL engine. QLever is an open-source project [1] but is not yet feature-complete.

We proposed using Scholia queries as a test suite for QLever¹⁰. This work extends that idea by demonstrating how to construct a test suite from SPARQL queries extractable from GitHub issues. A typical issue, such as the issue #896 CONCAT implementation¹¹, follows a standard situation/action/expected result format, which can be used for systematic testing and development.

The query set of 192 queries for the QLever use case is derived from queries extracted from QLever’s GitHub issues, performance queries related to DBLP documented on a wiki page in the GitHub repository, and example queries from the QLever-UI portal for the DBLP example dataset.

⁷ <https://query.wikidata.org/>

⁸ <https://scholia.toolforge.org/>

⁹ https://cr.bitplan.com/index.php/Semantic_Publishing_Challenge_Queries

¹⁰ <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever/issues/859>

¹¹ <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qlever/issues/896>

2.2 Definitions

To systematically address query rot, we introduce a layered approach to query management. At its core are Named Parameterized Queries (NPQs), which serve as an abstraction layer between query consumers and the actual query implementation. This abstraction allows query texts to be adapted to different Query Execution Contexts (QEC) while maintaining a consistent interface. A key limitation of SPARQL which lacks VIEW support is addressed this way. The interface is Interface Definition Language (IDL) input/processing/output specification compatible and technology agnostic federated queries become feasible see section 7.2.

We present two complementary definitions of **Query Execution Context (QEC)**: Definition 3 – a concrete/white-box definition for scholars, developers, people running the infrastructure and others with an interest in all graphic detail. Definition 2 – an abstract/black-box definition for general end users, system integrators and the general public. The white-box definition illustrates the high dimensionality of the solution space and cannot be elaborated in all detail here, while the black-box definition describes the simplified problem space that we intend to focus on in the core *query rot* Definition 4.

Definition 1 (Named Parameterized Query).

A Named Parameterized Query Q is a tuple (N, P, V, T) , where:

- N is the unique, fully qualified query name, structured as `name--namespace@domain`
- $P = (p_1 : t_1), \dots, (p_k : t_k)$ is the set of typed input parameters
- $V = (v_1 : t_1), \dots, (v_m : t_m)$ is the set of typed output variables
- T is a function that returns the query text based on the Query Execution Context

The query text function T enables different implementations of the same logical query to be served based on the execution context. The unique name convention is inspired by the Java Naming Convention [25].

Definition 2 (Query Execution Context (abstract/black-box)).

A Query Execution Context QEC is a function $QEC : QS \times G \rightarrow R$, where:

- $QS = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n\}$ is a set of Named Parameterized Queries as defined in Definition 1,
- G is the knowledge graph being queried,
- $R = (S, T, M)$ is the result, where S is an output stream, T is the content type, and M is metadata about the query execution.

Definition 3 (Query Execution Context (concrete/white-box)).

A Query Execution Context QEC is a function $QEC : QS \times G \times B \times EE \times L \rightarrow R$, where:

- $QS = \{q_i \mid i \in I\}$ is a set of Named Parameterized Queries, where each q_i is of type Q as defined in Definition 1, and I is an index set,

- $G = (V, E)$ is the knowledge graph being queried, where V represents the set of vertices and E represents the set of edges in the knowledge graph,
- $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k\}$ represents a set of boundary conditions,
- $EE = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m\}$ represents a set of execution environment parameters,
- L represents the query language standard and feature set,
- $R = (S, T, M)$ is the result, where S is an output stream, T is the content type, and M is metadata about the query execution.

The black-box definition reduces the complexity of the problem space to $QS \times G$, while the white-box definition exposes the full dimensionality of the solution space as $QS \times G \times B \times EE \times L$. The abstraction enables more effective knowledge engineering by simplifying the user’s conceptual model while allowing for complex optimizations in the implementation and providing standardized APIs independent of the hidden details.

An example of a Query Execution Context in practice would consist of QS being the Scholia Queryset “named_queries@scholia.toolforge.org” (see Section 2.1) consisting of more than 373 queries in the context of Wikidata as the knowledge graph G . Boundary conditions B include legal rules such as data protection and copyright laws, and limits set by organizational rules. The execution environment EE describes the Wikimedia Foundation’s data center running a cluster of Blazegraph instances and the 1 minute time out for the public Wikidata Query Service. L represents the SPARQL 1.1 language with Blazegraph extensions.

For the specific query

`author_events--named_queries@scholia.toolforge.org`, we have:

$N = \text{author_events--named_queries@scholia.toolforge.org}$

$P = \{(author : Q80)\}$ – Q80 is the Wikidata ID for Tim Berners-Lee

$V = \{(Date : xsd : dateTime), (Event : IRI), (EventLabel : xsd : string), (EventUri : IRI), (Roles : xsd : string), (Locations : xsd : string)\}$

An example output row for $R = (S, T, M)$:

S : HTML table containing a row: Date: 2009-10-25,

Event: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q48026503>, EventLabel: The 8th International Semantic Web Conference, EventUri: </event/Q48026503>, Roles: author, Locations: Washington, D.C.

T : HTML

M : {execution time: 0.4 seconds, result count: 25}

Definition 4 (Query Rot). *Query rot is a phenomenon that occurs when a Query Execution Context QEC, which previously produced satisfactory results for all queries $q \in QS$, experiences degradation or failure of query executions due to changes in underlying system components, despite no relevant changes to the query set QS or knowledge graph G . Query rot of a QEC manifests when for some q and some input parameter set of QS*

- q fails to execute,
- q returns unexpected, or inconsistent results, or

- the metadata of an execution q fails to meet specified functional or non-functional criteria or boundary conditions.

In the context of the white-box definition, query rot typically arises from unaccounted changes in:

- L : the query language standard or feature set,
- EE : the execution environment,
- B : the implicit or explicit boundary conditions, or
- G : the knowledge graph data or schema.

From the black-box perspective, query rot is observed as a change in the relationship between inputs (QS and KG) and output R , without apparent changes to these visible components.

3 Background and Related Work

3.1 Software Engineering Principles

Parnas introduced *Information Hiding* as a core principle of software engineering in his paper “On the Criteria to be Used in Decomposing Systems into Modules” [26]. He proposes modularization as a strategy to improve software quality. Parnas argues that instead of the conventional flowchart-based structure, a system decomposition approach should be applied: based on “information hiding”, it groups modules by hidden design decisions rather than processing steps.

Martin proposed the *Dependency Inversion Principle* [22] stating, “Depend upon Abstractions. Do not depend upon concretions”. This principle is a key strategy for achieving systematic information hiding. It advocates for the use of *black-box* intermediary interfaces to abstract away technical *white-box* implementation details, thereby reducing coupling between components and enhancing modularity, flexibility, and maintainability of software systems – thus reducing development time in the long run.

A comprehensive description of the state of the art of *Continuous Integration (CI)* and *Continuous Delivery (CD)* is given by Van Merode [23].

3.2 SPARQL

SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language) is the standard query language for RDF [7] data, recommended by the W3C, SPARQL 1.1 being the current version as of 2013 [15].

SPARQL allows for complex queries on linked RDF datasets by mapping variables to solutions represented as multisets of triples. Note that the results might not necessarily be “truly tabular” [13]. While SPARQL excels as a knowledge graph query language, its lack of standardized, technology-agnostic interfaces for producing results with guaranteed functional dependencies effectively mandates deeper technical coupling than many use cases require.

The traditional research approach applies a “white-box” view where the emphasis is on the technical and theoretical underpinnings, and all details are explored, such as in ontology design, having researchers and developers as a target group.

The formal analysis of the semantics of the SPARQL language by Perez et al. [27] is an example. It establishes the algebraic foundation of SPARQL based on graph patterns and RDF triples, contrasting with relational algebra, which operates on tables and lacks native support for optional data and flexible pattern matching.

The “white-box” view with end users and system integrators as a target group is somewhat underrepresented. Warren et al.’s work [31,30,32,33] is a notable exception. His work is rooted in the semantification of the BT Library, which is related to our scholarly publishing use case (Section 2.1). According to Warren [33], query expert knowledge is rare – 74% of his study participants claimed to have no knowledge at all. In a 2018 study [32], the minority of participants were end users and large databases with billions of triples were in the majority to be targeted by query sets. Timeouts were named as the main difficulty with SPARQL.

Lorey proposes latency, throughput, and execution time of joins as metrics for the quality of Query Execution Contexts [19]. He also worked on discovering query templates from query logs [21], which is analogous to introducing named parameterized queries. His PhD thesis “What’s in a Query: Analyzing, Predicting, and Managing Linked Data Access” [20] elaborates on the details.

The SPARQL standard does not call for enforcing structured error messages on failure: “The response body of a failed query request is implementation defined. Implementations may use HTTP content negotiation to provide human-readable or machine-processable (or both) information about the failed query request.” [14]

The introduction of parameterized queries to SPARQL was proposed as an addition to the W3C Standard by Vladimir Alexiev [2] in 2019. As of 2024, there are still only implementation-specific solutions.

3.3 Link Rot

Link rot describes cases where hyperlinks become invalid over time [28]. This happens when the target resource has been relocated to a new address (“re-route”) or has become permanently unavailable “dead”. A study on “link decay” by Hennessy for the time span 1999–2010 found that the median lifespan of web pages was 9.3 years [16]. Link rot breaks KG functionality and leads to frustrations, particularly in scholarly publishing contexts where citations rely on links [5]. One cause of Link rot is an orphaned responsibility for maintaining a link. Zhou et al. propose archiving links and predicting potential link failure to mitigate and avoid “404 Not Found” errors [36].

3.4 Query Rot

Query rot - the issue of query performance and stability over time (see Definition 4), has been indirectly addressed in various studies on SPARQL querying, such as Verborgh et al. “Querying Datasets on the Web with High Availability” [29], but has not been explicitly named or systematically studied before our work. There are several studies on mitigating the effects of schema evolution - a common change in the QEC which easily causes Query Rot: Hermann et al. [17] propose InVerDa, a Multi-Schema-Version Database Management System that allows multiple schema versions to co-exist within a single database while providing data independence through bidirectional schema modification operations, enabling agile database development with automatic delta code generation and workload-optimized physical materialization. The complexity of the problem is clearly shown by this study and is a high motivation to hide this complexity with a black-box approach. Curino et al. propose PRISM++ [6] to automate database migration and query/update rewriting during schema evolution, focusing particularly on preserving legacy applications. While providing important theoretical advances in schema mapping and rewriting, their approach requires detailed schema mappings that are more complex and harder for database administrators to create compared to snapquery’s higher-level SPARQL query set management.

4 Mitigating Query Rot using snapquery

The first step in mitigating Query Rot is to proactively identify when a query is no longer working as expected. Snapquery makes query sets available in computer readable form and has a command line and web interface to execute a query set against fitting endpoints and knowledge graphs. A whole Query Set of a project / Query Execution Context may be analyzed automatically this way, e.g., in a Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Delivery (CD) pipeline.

Figure 2 shows an example analysis. A difference in the number of failures and successes for a set of endpoints indicates potential Query Rot. In the example, the endpoints “Wikidata” and “Wikidata-scatter” should behave 100% identically, but they do not – an indicator that the QEC is not fully identical, e.g., the software versions and states of data are slightly different. Wikidata-qler performing differently on the examples and named-queries namespaces is to be expected since it does not support Blazegraph special syntax and is not feature complete yet.

4.1 Queries as FAIR first-class Knowledge Graph citizens

To make queries FAIR, we propose to use persistent identifiers for queries. Some SPARQL environments, such as the Wikidata Query Service and QLever, already offer the capability to create short URLs for queries, which may be used to uniquely identify a certain query text. Since the same query might

Legend: ✔ Distinct Successful Queries ✘ Distinct Failed Queries 📄 Total Successful Runs

Domain	Namespace	Total ↓	Wikidata	Wikidata-triply	Wikidata-qlEVER	Wikidata-openlinksw	Wikidata-scatter
scholia.toolforge.org	named_queries	373	✔109 ✘69 📄218	✔14 ✘312 📄28	✔11 ✘339 📄22	✔15 ✘346 📄30	✔108 ✘65 📄216
wikidata.org	examples	302	✔84 ✘21 📄168	✔5 ✘128 📄10	✔41 ✘249 📄82	✔48 ✘245 📄96	✔5 ✘0 📄10
qlEVER.cs.uni-freiburg.de	issues.wikidata	181	✔5 ✘176 📄10	✔33 ✘91 📄66	✔106 ✘32 📄212	✔83 ✘21 📄166	✔0 ✘52 📄0
wikidata.org	short_url	100	✔86 ✘7 📄172	✔7 ✘75 📄14	✔11 ✘85 📄22	✔13 ✘85 📄26	✔52 ✘1 📄104
ceur-ws.org	challenge	23	✔17 ✘7 📄68	✔12 ✘1 📄58	✔19 ✘5 📄72	✔18 ✘5 📄106	✔17 ✘7 📄68

Fig. 2: Query Set Success Overview

have different textual representations such as versions or platform specific adaptations, this approach is not fit to create persistent identifiers. Instead we propose to create PIDs from unique fully identifying names as per Definition 1 "Cats--examples@wikidata.org" is such a PID that may be translated to a corresponding URL that is usable in the RDF context and for RESTful APIs.

4.2 Local Query Execution Context Knowledge Graph

We propose a query management knowledge graph (KG) based on the core entities Query, Endpoint, SPARQL-Engine, Graph and Execution, which may be run locally.

Using such a local KG snapquery overcomes the current limitations of SPARQL by introducing platform-independent named parameterized queries and structured error reports ¹².

Figure 3 shows a UML class diagram for the core entities of the snapquery Query Execution Context KG.

Fig. 3: UML class diagram for core QEC entities

¹² (see Section 7.2) for corresponding SPARQL standard changes as future work

4.3 Semantification Workflow for Query Sets

Fig. 4: Semantification Workflow for a Query Execution Context

The flowchart in Figure 4 shows the snapquery Workflow for Query Execution Contexts (QEC), including semantification and agile refactoring with the goal of QEC optimization (see also wiki page¹³).

The process starts with FAIR Query Set resources (e.g., Wikipedia pages, GitHub issues) containing computer-readable queries. These are annotated using LLMs, human input, or specialized software, and stored in JSON format for import and visualization.

The Agile Refactoring Loop analyzes queries within a QEC, links them to Knowledge Graphs and endpoints, and modifies QEC elements and queries to improve execution. This iterative process continues until satisfactory quality is achieved, balancing all QEC aspects. The goal is to be less error-prone, faster, require annotators with minimal technical expertise, and allow for the proactive and automatic testing of query sets, e.g., as part of a CI/CD pipeline.

5 snapquery Implementation

The snapquery project is hosted on GitHub [11] and is available under the Apache 2.0 license. Links to further details and demos are found in the README.

The snapquery library is implemented in Python 3.9 or later. It utilizes a number of open source libraries for GUI, SPARQL, HTTP and Wiki handling,

¹³ https://cr.bitplan.com/index.php/QEC_Semantification_Workflow

authentication and other common tasks. Parts of the snapquery code have been developed with LLM support and a test-first attitude. snapquery is published via PyPI (version 0.0.12 as of 2024-07-12) and may be run locally.

snapquery is designed to be a SPARQL endpoint compatible middleware with RESTful APIs and a meta-query facility.

The snapquery design involves tradeoffs: it requires websockets and low-latency networks for optimal function, especially in real-time GUI interactions. Additionally, while aiming for compatibility with standard SPARQL endpoints, providing named parameterized queries is a non-standard feature necessitating client code modifications.

Running your own copies of Wikidata [12] is recommended but not necessary. We intend to make snapquery the backbone of an alternative Wikidata mirrors infrastructure as a mitigation measure.

6 Evaluation

6.1 Cats Wikidata Example

As stated in Section 1, most likely even the most prominent Wikidata SPARQL query example “Cats” will suffer from query rot. Applying the snapquery approach, we created an alternative query. Even though the original query only consists of one query pattern, it uses the Wikidata label service¹⁴, thus making the query incompatible with other endpoints and query engines, as the label service is only available in the Blazegraph Wikidata infrastructure. This can be seen in Figure 5a, as the query only executes successfully on the Wikidata endpoint and on Wikidata-scatter, a copy running the same infrastructure as Wikidata. On other endpoints running a copy of Wikidata with a different query engine, we see that the query fails every time with either a QueryBadFormed or EndpointInternalError error. By changing the query to directly query the *rdfs:label* instead of using the label service, the query becomes endpoint independent and executes on all endpoints successfully without increasing the execution time, as shown in Figure 5b.

6.2 Wikidata Thesis Toolkit

Query rot can occur when underlying data or schemas change, requiring updates to maintain query validity. This challenge affected the Wikidata Thesis Toolkit [35], a project by LSE and University of York libraries supporting the upload and management of doctoral thesis metadata in Wikidata.

Helen Williams and Ruth Elder, non-specialists in SPARQL, developed 27 queries for the toolkit. When informed about the upcoming Wikidata graph split¹⁵, they feared this effort might be lost. We used the snapquery approach to

¹⁴ a convention that automatically retrieves the labels for variables when "Label" is appended to the variable name in the SELECT clause.

¹⁵ https://m.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/WDQS_graph_split

Fig. 5: Execution statistics by endpoint of the cats query

quickly assess and adapt the queries: 1. Importing the query set from the toolkit wiki page, 2. Batch-testing all queries across split and legacy endpoints, 3. Identifying whether failures stemmed from endpoint issues or query/data changes.

6 of 27 queries required minor adjustments. All were revalidated on the split test endpoint in under a day—greatly alleviating concerns.

6.3 General Failure Reasons

snapquery provides an error message handling that filters and categorizes implementation dependent error message.

Table 2 shows error categories across different domains, namespaces, and endpoints as a result of trying the queries of Table 1 against different endpoints. Syntax errors are the most common issue, particularly for the *named_queries@scholia.toolforge.org* namespace, while endpoint internal errors and timeouts also pose significant challenges, especially for the *examples@wikidata.org* namespace. Systematic approaches may now be applied to solve the issues by further subcategorizing the errors.

6.4 LLM performance

Generating query annotations For the *short-url@wikidata.org* Query Set the annotation has been done automatically with gpt-3.5-turbo and gpt-4 via API. All 100 examples were successfully given a title, name and description. The result is in *wikidata-short-urls.json* in the samples of the GitHub project and available in the public demos. The prompt log is documented in our research wiki [8].

For the 100 queries, GPT-4 required an average execution time of 3.2 seconds per query and consumed 0.1 million tokens total. Manual inspection revealed fewer than 5 questionable annotations per 100 queries. With an estimated cost

Table 2: Top Query failure error categories grouped by namespace@domain

Error Category	Total Namespace@Domain	Endpoint
Syntax Error	3790 named_queries@scholia (2044), examples@wikidata (788), issues.wikidata@qlever (612), ...	wikidata-triply (1100), wikidata-qlever (996), ...
EndPoint-Internal	1142 examples@wikidata (624), short_url@wikidata (242), named_queries@scholia (140), ...	wikidata-openlinksw (642), wikidata-qlever (474), ...
Timeout	399 examples@wikidata (180), issues.wikidata@qlever (148), ...	wikidata-triply (342), wikidata (57)
Service Unavailable	82 issues.wikidata@qlever (26), examples@wikidata (20), ...	wikidata-triply (82)
Other	56 named_queries@scholia (28), examples@wikidata (24), ...	wikidata (18), wikidata-openlinksw (14), ...
Too Many Requests	20 named_queries@scholia (12), examples@wikidata (4), ...	wikidata (18),...

of less than \$0.01 per annotation (as of 2024-07), the automated approach not only provides clear efficiency advantages but also has the potential to provide consistent and higher quality annotations than typically achieved through human annotation.

The code for this task is available in our repository and could be scaled to thousands of Wikidata short URLs. LLM annotation has been implemented in snapquery but is restricted to authenticated users due to cost considerations.

Query rewriting We intend to test query rewriting with our tool to find how well standard refactoring activities would be supported by different Conversational AI tools. For a pre-selection of capable LLM, we did an experiment that is documented in our research wiki [9]. The prompts were: **Rewrite to make blazegraph independent** followed by the Cats Wikidata example source code as shown in Section 1. If the LLM did not produce a working SPARQL query, a second attempt was made using the prompt: **the result does neither work on the Wikidata query service nor on QLever**

Only one out of 4 LLMs could do the task on first attempt: ChatGPT-4o. Claude AI succeeded on the second attempt, Pi AI and Google Gemini failed. We intend to do further research with ChatGPT and Claude AI using the APIs.

7 Conclusion and Future Work

7.1 Conclusion

We introduce Query Rot and propose making Queries FAIR first-class citizens in a Knowledge Graph capturing Query Execution Context (QEC) metadata.

The snapquery method and tool enable a semantification workflow for Query Sets, systematically improving QEC quality faster and with less expert support. This approach separates concerns using a black-box named parameterized view for end-users and system integrators, while hiding details of the white-box view (visible for developers and scholars). As a middleware, snapquery provides hot-swappable queries, allowing preparation and testing of alternatives for upcoming changes such as the Wikidata graph split. The Wikidata Thesis Toolkit case (27 queries) demonstrates snapquery’s ability to enable proactive refactoring on QEC changes, particularly benefiting non-SPARQL specialists. This approach is currently extrapolated to larger cases such as Scholia (373 queries) and QLever (192 queries), potentially saving significant time and resources in maintaining and adapting larger query sets. By providing a framework for adapting to QEC changes, snapquery allows domain experts to focus on their primary tasks rather than worrying about knowledge graph query infrastructure.

7.2 Future Work

We intend to finalize the work on the three use cases presented – providing benchmarks, test suites and challenges based on the corresponding Query Sets. Prior SPARQL query log work can be revisited using the snapquery approach, with the goal of making the results more stable against QEC changes.

By separating query declaration from execution details, snapquery enables technology-agnostic JOIN operations across SPARQL endpoints, other relational and graph databases and Web APIs, enabling research on new approaches for federated query management.

The LLM-supported query refactoring activities for Scholia and QLever, with the goal of integrating snapquery into the CI/CD pipelines, will be in our focus.

Developing a comprehensive Query Execution Context Ontology is a worthwhile research goal.

We propose the following improvements to the W3C SPARQL standard:

1. Native support for named parameterized queries.
2. Standardized metadata for queries.
3. Structured error reporting.
4. Default prefix declarations per QEC.
5. Generally making queries FAIR first-class citizens.

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